

Target Costing: A Strategic Management Accounting Tool for Enhancing Institutional Competitiveness

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Abstract

The study examined target costing as a strategic management accounting tool for enhancing institutional competitiveness. In the context of financial targets and target control, the study investigated the awareness and application of target costing among top performing and highly ranked Nigerian Private Universities. The sample frame is accredited private universities. To ensure regional diversity for the scope of the study, universities were selected from the southwest, North-Central and North-East. The study adopted purposive sampling techniques to arrive at top Five (5) private universities who have consistently ranked high by the annual university ranking systems. Primary data for the study were gathered through questionnaire administered to Vice-chancellors, Registrars, Bursars, Directors and Student Alumni. The study employed Partial Least Square Structural Adjustment Model (PLS-SEM) to test the hypothesis arising from the objectives of the study. Against the 0.5 threshold, the results indicated significant relationships between target costing strategies and institutional competitiveness as Financial Targets shows strong indicator loadings (0.872, -0.991, 0.863) for cost savings, specific targets, and tuition budgets, while Targets Control demonstrates robust loading (0.999) for target review updates. Several measures exceed the 0.5 threshold to validate the parameters as reliable indicators of competitiveness. It was concluded that, while strong target control mechanisms is crucial for competitiveness, overly rigid financial targets may be counterproductive. Universities should focus on flexible, adaptive target control systems rather than strict financial constraints to enhance their competitive position, and equally institutionalize comprehensive targets control frameworks, leveraging periodic reviews and real-time adjustments to review cost strategies.

Keywords: Target costing, Financial targets, Target control, University competitiveness

Word count: 249

Introduction

Universities are expected to be adequately funded so that they can accomplish the purpose of quality teaching, research and community services. Obviously, Nigerian public universities are confronted with funding issues that in many cases, had degenerated into industrial disharmony. Conversely, the success stories of some top private universities, has underscored the need to evaluate the indices in the private educational sector that have supported academic excellence and financial prudence of the high performing private universities in Nigeria. However, the private sector is characterised by the high rate of competition that has in most cases prompted the adoption of strategies to gain competitive advantage. Amid increased competition in higher education landscape, universities now face increased pressure to deliver high quality academic programmes, research and community services while managing costs and resources efficiently. Michael porter theory of competitive strategy gave a framework to achieve competitive strategies through three distinct strategies: Cost leadership, Differentiation strategy and Focus strategy (Porter, 1980). Consequently, to remain competitive in the market, there is the need for modern and informed cost management techniques such as Target Costing. Target costing involves setting cost targets based on market-driven prices. Target costing is more pronounced in the manufacturing companies because of the direct link between the cost of production and profitability as many manufacturing companies have been using target costing as a strategic weapon to enhance profitability, however, the practice has just been gaining popularity among service companies.

According to Sabelo (2022) target costing is a known cost management tool that assists in ensuring costs management and keeping fees low. This argument suffices for the need for institutions to begin to adopt the target costing approach to mitigate the effect of shortfall in government spending. As Nigerian universities face significant challenges in maintaining competitiveness in the global education landscape, there seem to be unanswered questions on how application of target costing can strengthen their competitiveness (Oyedokun, Tomomewo, & Owolabi, 2019). Moreso, there appear to be paucity of empirical studies among Nigerian universities on this topic. This study therefore aims to investigate how target costing has been applied in the university settings for cost efficiency and optimal resource allocation. The study also examined the benefits and challenges of implementing target costing in the universities, and how target costing practices contributed to the improvement of academic programme quality, student satisfaction, and institutional competitiveness.

Literature Review

Pricing Decision

In a general sense, price is what is given up to acquire goods or services. McDaniel, Lamb, and Hair (2011) says price plays roles as a measure of sacrifice and information cue. Pricing decision is the process of making a choice among numerous prices. Prices are key to revenue and profit of an organization, therefore to make profit, manager must choose price that is not too high or low, but equal to the perceived value to target consumers. Price element is a core element of free-market economy, and in a highly competitive business environment, managerial pricing decision making tends to be critical. Kotler and Armstrong (2014) considers market penetration pricing as one of the pricing decisions to win a large market share by setting low initial price to penetrate the market quickly and deeply. McDaniel, Lamb and Hair (2011) viewed pricing decision from three perspectives: profit maximization, sales-oriented pricing and status quo pricing objectives. The third category entails maintaining existing prices to meet the competition's prices. Consequently, in setting prices, companies totally are not free to charge whatever prices they wish because many federal, state and local government law govern the rules of fair play (Oyedokun, Tomomewo, & Owolabi, 2019).

Cost Decisions

Cost is resources spent to acquire, produce or provide a product, services or activity. The process of cost ascertainment involves establishment of what it actually cost to produce a complete a job. Lucey (2003) recognizes cost as either direct or indirect cost. Direct cost are the costs comprising direct materials, direct labour and direct expenses. Indirect costs are all materials, labour and expenses which cannot be identified directly with the product, so they are termed as overhead. Overheads are analyzed into the categories appropriate for the organization. The combination of direct material, direct labour and direct expenses brings about what is known as prime cost, while prime cost and overhead gives the total cost. Some of the common costing methods include: (i) Job Costing: the purpose of which to establish profit or loss on each completed job. (ii) Batch Costing: used where quantity of identical articles is produced together example, clothing and footwear. Batch costing treats each batch as a single job. (iii) Contract Costing is peculiar to product of long production duration, undertaken to the customer's specific specification. A peculiar feature is the provision for progress payment to be made by the client. (iv) Process Costing is adopted where product follows a series of sequential, frequently automated process. The essence of process costing is the averaging of the total cost of each process over the total throughput, charging the cost of output of one process as the cost of material input to the next process (Oyedokun, Tomomewo, & Owolabi, 2019).

Concept of Target Costing

As against cost-plus pricing that takes no account of customers' willingness and ability to pay, the concept of target costing has made factors such as customer ability, price sensitivity of demand, competitors' prices for similar products, and the market positioning, important variables which must be consciously considered as part of a strategic approach to pricing. According to Osisoma Egbunike, Okafor and Okoye, (2021) target costing is a strategic management accounting tool developed majorly by Japanese manufacturers which dates back to the 2nd World War, when they made efforts to rebuild their economy. Hamood and Omar (2011) mentioned that for successful adoption of target costing, companies should give much attention to the influential factors related to the product development strategy and customers' expectations through the market research process. The basic standard of target costing is that the cost of producing and distributing a product must not exceed competitively realistic selling price. It is not about whether or not a proposed selling price is fair, but rather whether it is competitively realistic and strategically appropriate. Target costing, in contrast to cost-plus pricing, provides a means of taking explicit note of these factors and provides a framework for an integrated strategic approach to pricing and cost management. Some factors to consider in applying target costing should include homogeneity of products, level of competition, switching costs for the end customer. Target costing is expressed as selling price less profit margin. Target costing assists in making the new product competitive in terms of cost, quality and functionality (Target Cost = Selling Price – Required Profit). By and large, Hence, the concept target costing is not just a method of costing, rather a management technique wherein prices are determined by market conditions.

Financial Targets and Target Control components of Target Costing

Previous literatures have set a proper context for target costing as predetermined cost level that a company aims to achieve based on market conditions, customer expectation and competitor analysis (Hamood & Omar, 2011); (Sabelo, 2022; Oyedokun, Olatayo, & Adeyemo, 2023). Financial target involves setting specific financial goals, such as cost reduction, revenue growth or profitability targets which serve as a guide to target costing process and ensure alignment with overall business objectives. Target control is a mechanism used to monitor and control costs during the target costing process. This includes budgeting, forecasting and variance analysis. Thango (2022) highlighted the required steps for target costing as enunciated by Cooper and Slagmulder (1999), to be range of exercises spanning from conducting market research to the competitor analysis, determining customer interests, defining customer product features, determining the market price, determining the required profit to arriving at targeted costs. It is, however, clear from the above that target control is essential to achieving target costing objective. By establishing target cost, a company can set a clear financial target for cost reduction and management, monitor and control cost, identify address variances, then adjust strategies and plan (Oyedokun, Dopemu, & Adejuwo, 2024).

Barriers to Target Costing

Kim, Ansari, Bell and Swenson (2002) found that the biggest barrier to target costing are resources and rewards, noting that there are often limited resources to implement it, while there are few rewards for achieving targets, whereas missing targets are viewed negatively. Other barriers include poor accounting information system, lack of familiarity, and lack of cross-functional cooperation. Another obvious shortcoming is the extensive focus on the cost drivers and neglect the revenue drivers whereas, the revenue drivers may include random market changes such as technology and customer needs and wants. Another limitation is that of time, especially the case when an organization's good financial performance relies on technology and time-to-market. This means that the teams responsible for product development may not focus on alternative searches and estimate their effects on the final product, rather have no choice but to choose the one that reduces the costs. The other limitations is that of viewing target costing as being too linear with a large amount of bureaucracy and the level of details required. Even among companies in the developed countries, only a small number have been using target costing for a very long time (Kim, Ansari, Bell & Swenson, 2002; Oyedokun, Dopemu, & Adejuwo, 2024).

Target Costing and Competitive Strategies

Competitive advantage implies making products and services superior from the point of view of consumers in comparison to other similar products offered in the market. Gaining a competitive advantage is the goal of every organization. McDaniel, Lamb and Hair (2011) stated that Strategic planning is a managerial process of creating and maintaining a fit between the organization objectives and resources and the evolving opportunities. Porter (1998) argued that every organization has a strategy whether implicit or explicit to cope with the competitive forces. According to him, the three generic strategies are the major business strategies which are cost leadership, differentiation strategies, and segmentation strategies have been useful weapons in the modern-day organizations. The current study aligns with cost leadership objective through financial targets and target control. The results of prior studies including Al-Awawdeh and Al-Sharairi (2012), Sabelo (2022) and Swenson, Ansari, Bell, and Kim (2003) indicate that target cost management system has a significant relationship with corporate competitiveness, because companies using target cost management system have reported an increased profitability. Ejike (2002) aligned with the view of Osioma, Egbunike, Okafor and Okoye (2021) that, in order to achieve a competitive advantage, costs should be conducted to a point it does not surpass the predetermined selling price and the lowest possible amount of expected profit. Al-Awawdeh and Al-Sharairi (2012) stated that the concept of target costing technique is relatively recent in educational institutions, but a potential strategy for competitive strategy (Oyedokun, Dopemu, & Adejuwo, 2024).

Theoretical Review

Hinterhuber (2004) reviewed value-based pricing proposed by Shipley and Jobber (2001) as an integrative framework for decision making. It entails setting prices based on the perceived value of a product or services. He said the starting point is a clear definition of the objectives of the pricing process, followed by the three critical elements of strategic decisions, from the company perspective, from the customer perspective, and from the competitive perspective. Each perspective is then related to one specific tool to capture the implications for pricing purposes. By implication, price is determined by customer's willingness to pay, influenced by product or service benefit, perceived value, price elasticity and competitive advantage. Furthermore, the concept of Activity Based Costing (ABC) has recently gained prominence by its method of charging overheads to cost units on the basis of benefit received from a particular indirect activity. The ABC entails: (i) identification of main activities in the organization (ii) identification of factors which determine the cost of an activity also known as cost drivers. (iii) Collection of the cost of each activities in (i) above; otherwise known as cost pools. (iv) charging overhead to product on the basis of their usage of activity, in terms of chosen cost drivers. Basically, ABC ensures accurate costing by assigning cost to activities rather than department and products. Cropper and Cook (2010) analyzed activity based costing in the context of university value proposition as follows: identify the resource costs (staff, consumables, equipment etc.) identify the products (courses, research papers, consultancy, catering etc.) Identify the activities (course delivery, research, admissions, library services etc.) assign resource costs to activities by linking the activities to the products using cost drivers (staff, students, space). He concluded that Activity Based Costing as Strategic element of Strategic Management Accounting is, in principle, applicable to all educational institutions, but practically requires a high level of commitment, training, communication, data collection, processing and interpretation of work as well as the consequent need for resources and funding for its development.

Empirical Review

Kim, Ansari, Bell and Dan-Swenson (2002) studied target costing practice in United State by gathering survey data from adopters and non-adopters of target costing. Questionnaires were administered to 1564 members of the Cost Management Section of the Institute of Certified Public Accountants. It was found that most companies (both adopters and non-adopters) use more than one approach in pricing the same product. Surprisingly, the most common approach is cost plus a required profit margin. It was also revealed that Adopters solicit and implement employee suggestions more frequently than non-adopters. Also, large companies tend to use target costing more than small companies.

Thango, Nzuza and Marimuthu (2024) explored the factors influencing the adoption of target costing by higher education institutions in South Africa, along with the potential implications for

pricing strategies. Utilizing both closed-ended and open-ended questions in a questionnaire survey targeting 52 heads of departments and 15 finance staff members, the results showed that target costing had not been fully used but existed in selected areas of the university. Findings further revealed that costs of fees are subject to historic judgment, implying that they are not reworked annually. Many respondents perceive the cost-plus pricing methods to be the best for the university. The respondents gave a lack of expertise in target costing as the reason for partial adoption of target costing at the university. The findings further indicated that institution size, data management system adequacy, staff collaboration, support, resource availability, and sector competition significantly impact the delay and rejection of target costing adoption.

Al-Awawdeh and Al-Sharairi (2012) explored the relationship between target costing and competitiveness at Jordanian private universities. Using a structured questionnaire, two scales were used to measure the estimates by financial managers, directors of planning and quality, and heads of accounting departments in the universities. The sample size was 50 respondents, and response rate was 80%. Results showed a significant difference in the strength of links between the dimensions of the target costing technique and the dimensions of strengthening the competitive advantage. Findings of the study indicated that universities have a medium target costing dimensions of (3.48); the dimension of target selling price leadership was the highest and reducing the life cycle of university specialization was the lowest; universities enjoy a medium competitive advantage with a score of (3.46)

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research design. The scope of the study was the southwest Nigeria, the North-Central and North-East. Nigeria private universities constitute the best context for the study due to their financial autonomous status and their business nature that often support innovative approaches to education and financial management. Moreover, private universities would provide a deeper understanding of the factors that contribute to their success and help to identify potential strategies for improvement that can be applied to other institutions.

The study adopted purposive sampling techniques to select top Five (5) reputable private universities who have existed for at least the past Five (5) years, who have consistently ranked high by the annual university ranking system. The selected universities were also based on research opportunities and geographical diversity. The key respondents were Vice-chancellors, Registrars, and Bursars, Directors and Student /Alumni. Data was gathered through structured questionnaires containing items solicited information on target costing practices in the institution

The study employed empirical analysis tools including descriptive statistics, normality test on the Skewness and Kurtosis, Fornell-Larcker criterion confirmed the discriminant validity, while

multicollinearity test was conducted to assess the correlation between the independent variable. Other analyses were constructing reliability and validity to demonstrate the reliability and validity of constructs used to evaluate the adoption of target costing in private universities, and bootstrapping showed path coefficients and more insights into the relationships between variables (Oyedokun, 2020). The hypotheses arising from the objectives of the study were tested using Partial Least Square Structural Adjustment Model (PLS-SEM). The model was assessed through a path model to determine the effect of target costing on competitiveness of Nigeria highly rated private universities.

Limitations and Future Studies

The study targeted five (5) participants from each university drawn from the Principal Officers, with the hope of gathering responses from 25 respondents as sample size. Two of the universities returned only one (1) questionnaire each as the consensus opinion of the entire principal officers. Two other universities returned three (3) completed questionnaire each. The researcher resorted to student version of the questionnaire to gather information from the students in order to make up for the only university that did not respond. Future studies should extend the scope of the study to a larger number of universities, probably to include a mixture of highly and lowly ranked universities for more diverse samples to identify some limiting factors not captured. Further studies could adopt an interview method for data gathering from the key principal officers to provide more information about the relationship between variables. Future studies could also consider student admission enrollment from the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examinations (UTME) as a basis of measuring and selecting competitive universities

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1 Descriptive Analysis and Normality Test

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Excess Kurtosis	Skewness
Academic Excellence	4.300	1.005	0.589	-1.319
Cost Savings Target	4.600	0.490	-2.018	-0.442
Department Consideration	4.400	0.663	-0.446	-0.712
Differentiation Strategy	4.500	1.025	1.739	-1.812
Discipline Maintenance	4.600	0.490	-2.018	-0.442
Fees Attraction	4.000	1.000	-0.671	-0.650
Global Recognition	4.300	1.005	0.589	-1.319
International School Fees	3.500	1.285	-1.833	0.153
Modern Facilities	4.500	0.500	-2.235	
National School Fees	4.300	1.100	-0.389	-1.152

Need Response	4.000	1.000	-0.671	-0.650
Program Introduction	4.200	0.980	0.359	-1.133
Quality Facilities	4.100	0.943	0.335	-0.991
Ranking	4.300	0.900	2.267	-1.569
Specific Cost Target	4.700	0.458	-1.242	-0.945
Standard Recruitment	4.400	1.020	1.036	-1.544
Student Parent Relationship	4.000	1.000	-0.671	-0.650
Students Enrollment Target	4.600	0.490	-2.018	-0.442
Target Reviews and Update	4.500	0.500	-2.235	
Tuition/ Program Budget Target	4.300	0.781	-1.108	-0.627

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

The table highlights the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis for key variables related to competitiveness in Nigerian private universities. "Specific Cost Target" had the highest mean (4.7), indicating strong emphasis by respondents on setting specific cost targets as part of strategic management accounting. In contrast, "International School Fees" recorded the lowest mean (3.5), signaling limited alignment with international tuition benchmarks. Standard deviations were lowest for "Cost Savings Target" and "Discipline Maintenance" (0.49), indicating consensus among respondents. Skewness values for most variables were negative, showing left-skewed data, while kurtosis revealed a mix of platykurtic and leptokurtic distributions. These patterns imply that strategic cost management and target costing are embraced to varying degrees, with specific focus areas like "Specific Cost Target" achieving more acceptance, reflecting its competitive advantage in private universities. The result aligns with Thango, Nzuza and Marimuthu (2024) that reported that target costing had not been fully used but exists in selected areas of the university.

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between financial target setting, target control mechanism, and university competitiveness

Assessment of Measurement Model

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

The structural model in figure 1 reveals significant relationships between target costing strategies and institutional competitiveness in Nigerian private universities. Evaluating against the 0.5 benchmark, Financial Targets shows strong indicator loadings (0.872, -0.991, 0.863) for cost savings, specific targets, and tuition budgets, while Targets Control demonstrates robust loading (0.999) for target review updates, validating these measurement items. The relationship between Financial Targets and institutional competitiveness shows a negative impact (-0.466), suggesting that strict financial controls might hinder competitiveness. However, Targets Control exhibits a strong positive influence (1.131) on competitiveness, indicating that effective monitoring and adjustment of targets enhances competitive position. Regarding institutional competitiveness indicators, several measures exceed the 0.5 threshold, notably discipline maintenance (0.621), program introduction (0.710), and modern facilities (-0.895), validating these as reliable indicators of competitiveness. The implications for Nigerian private universities are significant. While maintaining strong target control mechanisms is crucial for competitiveness, overly rigid financial targets may be counterproductive. This suggests institutions should focus on flexible, adaptive

target control systems rather than strict financial constraints to enhance their competitive position in the education sector.

Table 2 Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Financial Targets	0.930	0.935	0.829
Institutions' Competitiveness	0.714	0.790	0.584
Targets Control	0.780	0.783	0.567

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 2 presents the construct reliability and validity. This table demonstrates the reliability and validity of constructs used to evaluate the adoption of target costing in private universities. Financial Targets achieved Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.930, indicating high internal consistency, while Composite Reliability (CR) of 0.935 further confirms this. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values surpass the threshold of 0.5, confirming convergent validity for all constructs. These results validate the reliability of the measurement model, ensuring that constructs like "Financial Targets" and "Institutional Competitiveness" are robust for assessing how target costing drives competitive strategies.

Table 3 Discriminant Validity

	Financial Targets	Institutions' Competitiveness	Targets Control
Financial Targets	0.910		
Institutions' Competitiveness	0.201	0.764	
Targets Control	0.589	0.856	0.753

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 3 presents the discriminant validity. The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to confirm discriminant validity. The diagonal values represent square roots of AVE and are higher than inter-construct correlations, indicating that constructs like "Financial Targets" (0.910) and "Targets Control" (0.753) are distinct. A notable correlation exists between "Targets Control" and "Institutions' Competitiveness" (0.856), suggesting a significant relationship. This reinforces the role of robust target controls in enhancing competitive positioning, a key strategic imperative for private universities.

Table 4 Inner VIF Values

	Financial Targets	Institutions' Competitiveness	Targets Control
Financial Targets		1.532	
Institutions' Competitiveness			
Targets Control		1.532	

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 4 presents the inner VIF values. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values were all 1.532, below the threshold of 5. This confirms no significant multicollinearity among the independent variables. By avoiding redundancy in the data, the model ensures accurate estimations of relationships between "Financial Targets," "Targets Control," and "Institutions' Competitiveness," highlighting that target costing initiatives are well-structured for effective strategy implementation.

Table 5 Bootstrapping Results Showing Path Coefficient for Structural Model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Financial Targets -> Institutions' Competitiveness	-0.466	-0.070	0.489	0.953	0.341
Targets Control -> Institutions' Competitiveness	1.131	0.559	0.950	1.190	0.235

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 5 presents bootstrapping results showing path coefficients. The path coefficients provide insights into the relationships between variables. "Targets Control" had a significant positive effect on "Institutions' Competitiveness" ($\beta = 1.131$, $T = 1.190$), albeit not statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($p = 0.235$). "Financial Targets," however, showed a negative effect ($\beta = -0.466$, $T = 0.953$) and were also not statistically significant ($p = 0.341$). These results suggest that while target control mechanisms influence competitiveness positively, financial targets alone may not directly drive competitive outcomes, underlining the need for a balanced approach.

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination Score

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Institutions' Competitiveness	0.875	0.861

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 6 presents the coefficient of determination (R-Square). An R-squared value of 0.875 indicates that 87.5% of the variance in "Institutions' Competitiveness" is explained by "Financial Targets" and "Targets Control." The adjusted R-squared (0.861) confirms this robustness, highlighting the strong predictive power of the model. This underscores the pivotal role of target costing practices in explaining competitive dynamics within Nigerian private universities.

Table 7 Assessment of the Effect Size (f²)

	Financial Targets	Institutions' Competitiveness	Targets Control
Financial Targets		1.136	
Institutions' Competitiveness			
Targets Control		6.694	

Source: SmartPLS Output, 2025

Table 7 presents the effect size (f²). The effect size analysis revealed a substantial impact of "Targets Control" on "Institutions' Competitiveness" (f² = 6.694) and a moderate impact for "Financial Targets" (f² = 1.136). These findings emphasize that robust target controls significantly contribute to competitive positioning, further validating the strategic importance of this construct in the university context.

Results and Discussions

The study revealed that "Targets Control" positively influences competitiveness by highlighting its strategic importance in monitoring and refining cost objectives to align with competitive goals. This result agrees with Osioma, Egbunike, Okafor and Okoye (2021) who found that target costing enhances cost advantage in a competitive environment. Conversely, "Financial Targets" alone exhibited a negative effect, suggesting a need for targets to integrate with broader strategic initiatives. This revelation aligns with Al-Awawdeh and Al-Sharairi (2012) who discovered a significant difference in the strength of links between the dimensions of the target costing technique and the dimensions of strengthening the competitive advantage. Both constructs demonstrated strong reliability and validity, confirming their appropriateness for examining competitiveness. The results from Thango, Nzuza and Marimuthu (2024) support the findings of the study that target costing practices explain a significant portion of competitive dynamics, but their efficacy depends on effective implementation and alignment with institutional priorities. This

is suggestive of the need for Nigerian private universities to refine these strategies to maximize their impact.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Interestingly, the study reveals that top universities were inadvertently applying target costing principles in their financial management practices despite lacking explicit awareness or intention. The study therefore concludes that Targets Control is a pivotal variable driving competitiveness in Nigerian private universities, emphasizing the importance of structured cost monitoring and review mechanisms. Financial Targets, though integral, require a balanced approach incorporating strategic dimensions to drive meaningful outcomes. These findings underscore the need for private universities to adopt a holistic approach to target costing, blending financial objectives with robust control measures to enhance institutional competitiveness sustainably.

From the above, the study recommends as follows:

- i. Private universities in Nigeria should institutionalize comprehensive "Targets Control" frameworks, leveraging periodic reviews and real-time adjustments to refine cost strategies.
- ii. University administrators must integrate "Financial Targets" with strategic initiatives, focusing on long-term value creation.
- iii. Nigerian universities should collaborate with international universities that have successfully implemented target costing for actionable insights. Implementation should begin within six months, starting with pilot programs in departments with high financial impact, and eventually scaling university-wide. This approach will ensure that target costing becomes a cornerstone of competitive strategy in Nigerian private universities.

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